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A STUDY ON TECHNOLOGY USED FOR EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT OF SOLAR PV CELLS

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Abstract:

Solar PV cells are building material for solar power Plants. Like all other electrical devices the efficiency improvement is a major research topic these days. In practice, high-energy conversion efficiency and long effective service time can help in reducing capital and operating costs, and, thus, are highly desired. Efficiency of solar PV cells depends upon many factors including environmental and the aging of PV cells. The technology such as Array mounting and Tracking is proved to be efficient for improving the performance of solar PV cells. The conversion efficiency of solar PV cells is directly proportional to the amount of direct solar irradiance that is absorbed. The solar tracker device moves or adjusts the positional angle of photo voltaic cells towards sun.

Key Words- solar Array mounting and tracking, Nano studs.

INTRODUCTION

The crystalline PV solar cell shown in Figure 1 is a solid state semiconductor p-n junction device that converts sunlight into direct-current through the principle of photo-voltaic effect. The first photovoltaic cells were produced in the late 1950s, and were principally deployed to provide electrical power for orbital satellites. During this initial deployment, excessive manufacturing cost and low efficiency of solar modules were few of the major challenges that limit their competitiveness to meet the increasing energy demand that has now been compensated somehow. Recent research and design in the field of solid state devices and material science has led some improvement in manufacturing cost, performance and quality of solar cells. Reduced cost of modules have not only opened up the doors for their deployments in applications like telecommunications equipment, critical military installations, powering remote terrestrial applications, rural electrification projects, battery charging for navigational aids and water pumping, but has also propelled solar power system as a competitive means to meet the ever increasing power need for the world economy. The focus of this thesis is to improve the efficiency of solar PV cells; in the process it is important to take some cursory, but refreshing look at the semiconductor physics of a solar cell.

Fig.1: solar PV cell [2]

2. IDEAL SOLAR CELL

When a solar cell is illuminated by sun-light, (Figure 1), photons energy of the incident light is converted to direct current through the process of photovoltaic effect of the solar cell. Incident light causes electron-hole pairs to be generated in the semiconductor and there is increase in the concentration of minority carriers (electrons in the p-type region and holes in the n-type region) in the depletion region. This results in the flow of the minority carriers across the depletion region into the quasi-neutral regions. These photo-generated carriers cause the flow of photo-generated current, I_{photons} . When the junction is in the open-circuit condition, no net current can flow inside the p-n junction, thus the current resulting from the flux of photo-generated and thermally-generated carriers is balanced by the opposite recombination current.

Fig. 2: Incident light on a typical PN solar cell [1]

When the load is connected between the electrodes of the illuminated p-n junction, then fraction of the photo-generated current flows through the external circuit. The potential difference between the n-type and p-type regions will be lowered by a voltage drop over the load. Also a decrease in electrostatic potential difference over the depletion region is seen which results in an increase of the recombination current. Applying superposition theorem, the total current flowing through the load is determined as the sum of the photo-and thermal generation currents and the recombination current as shown in the IV-characteristic curves (Figure2).

Fig. 3: V-I characteristic curves of a p-n junction in the dark and under illumination [1].

3. EVOLUTION OF SOLAR CELLS & EFFICIENCY

3.1 1st Generation Solar Cells (Crystalline silicon (c-Si) PV-technology):

Photo-voltaic effect was first recognized by the French physicist, Alexandre-Edmond Becquerel in 1839. The first modern solar cell with enough efficiency for power applications was developed in 1954 at Bell Labs in New Jersey. While experimenting with semiconductors, Bell lab found that silicon doped with certain impurities is highly sensitive to light. This is the evolution of 1st generation solar cell technology. C-Si PV is a Silicon-based technology and it captures more than 86% of the solar cell market. It has become the most dominant technology in the commercial production of solar cells. It is technically proven and reliable, primarily in off-grid remote areas and lately in grid-Connected applications. There are some limitations to the C-Si generation PV technology. The Silicon wafers are extremely fragile and the difficult and labor intensive manufacturing process makes it costly.

Fig 4: Efficiency milestone of crystalline based solar cell [1]

The crystalline silicon based solar cells are manufactured in two ways; single crystal and multi-crystalline cells. Single crystal silicon wafers (c-Si) or the Mono-Crystalline Solar Cells is still one of the most efficient photovoltaic solar cells to date. In mono-crystalline PV cells, for the entire wafer, the crystal lattice is continuous and also unbroken with no grain boundaries. The process of production involves extraction of crystalline silicon rods from melted silicon and then sawed into thin plates. About half of the manufacturing cost comes from wafering; a time-consuming and costly batch process in which ingots are cut into thin wafers with a thickness of about 200 micrometers. The polycrystalline approach is cheaper than the single crystalline cells as it uses discrete cells on silicon wafers cut from multi-crystalline ribbons; whereas in single crystalline cells the wafers are very thin, which will break in the process and due to this thickness requirement, a PV cell requires a significant amount of raw silicon and close to half of this not very inexpensive material is lost as sawdust in the wafer processes. The average price for single-crystal modules is ranged up to \$3.97 per peak watt compared to \$2.43 for poly-crystal modules. Though it is more expensive, Mono-crystalline silicon cells are more durable and efficient. It produces more wattage per square foot than the polycrystalline cell of the same specifications. These crystalline silicon based solar cells have broad spectral absorption range and high carrier mobility. The efficiency of mono-crystalline silicon solar cell currently is about 28% while poly-crystalline cells are ranged up to 20%. Please see the chart below in Figure.4 for efficiency milestone of crystalline based solar cell.

The main properties of polycrystalline PV module are [3]

- Efficiency: 13% to 16 %.
- Form: Square.
- Thickness: 0.24mm to 0.3mm.
- Color: blue (with ARC), silver, grey, brown, gold and green (without ARC)

3.2 2ND Generation Solar Cells: Thin-film Technology Solar Cells:

Because of the high cost of manufacturing of the 1st generation solar cells, a 2nd Generation solar cells known as thin film technologies was developed. The technology involves depositing a thin layer of photo-active material (Non-crystalline silicon) onto inexpensive substrates material using plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) process. Amorphous semiconductor material (a-Si) is commonly used. An amorphous material differs from crystalline material in that there is no long-range order in the structural arrangement of the atoms. The efficiency of the thin film PV cells is significantly lower though they are less subjected to breakage and not vulnerable to most of the other manufacturing problems that are common to the crystalline solar cells. There are also some concerns about the toxic legacy of the materials both in manufacturing and at the end of life. The amorphous solar cells shown in Figure 5 are quite flexible to install and also less support is needed when placing panels on rooftops. The efficiency of thin film technologies solar cell is approaching about 20% based on recent research breakthroughs.

Figure 5 Amorphous solar cells [1]

The thin film technology has many advantages though it has low efficiency when compared to crystalline technology [4]:

- Better utilization of diffuse and low light intensity.
- Less sensitive to higher operating temperature
- Less sensitive to shading because of long narrow strip design, while a shaded cell on crystalline module will affect the whole module.
- Energy yield at certain condition is higher than crystalline technology.

The main properties of amorphous silicon PV module are [4]:

- In stabilized condition the Efficiency of the module is up to 5% to 7%.
- Thickness is about 1mm to 3mm substrate material, with approximately 0.001mm (1 μ m) coating, of which approximately 0.3 μ m amorphous silicon.
- These modules come in the reddish brown to blue or blue-violet colour.

3.3 3rd Generation Solar Cells:

The 3rd generation solar cells involve different Semiconductor Technologies that are fundamentally different from the previous semiconductor devices. These generation PV cells technologies are estimated that it will achieve higher efficiencies and lower manufacturing and installation costs than 1st or 2nd generation technologies [4]. These technologies are Nanocrystal Solar Cells, Photo-electrochemical cells, Dye-sensitized hybrid solar cells and Polymer Solar cells. The Nano crystal solar cell technology is based on quantum dots or grains of Nanocrystals. Some examples are Lead selenide (PbSe) semiconductor and Cadmium telluride (CdTe) semiconductor. The band-Gaps of Quantum dots are tunable and hence can be tuned by changing the quantum dot size across a wide range of energy levels. Whereas the band-gap of crystalline material is fixed, based on the material composition. This property makes quantum dots viable for multi-junction solar cells, where a variety of different band-gap materials are used to optimize efficiency by harvesting select portions of the solar spectrum. Additional advantages of these cells are; Low material cost and high-throughput processing technologies, low energy, the 3rd generation cells perform even at low incident light conditions. The disadvantage of this type cell is that the efficiency is lower than silicon wafer based solar cells and also there is a risk of material degradation over a span of time. The efficiency of this type of solar cell is about 11%.

Hence the other advantages of CIS are:

- Low cost processing method. It uses less than 1/200 active material as compared to crystalline silicon.
 - It has a wide range of spectrum response for the sun light.
 - Among thin film technology it has the highest module efficiency.
- The main properties for CIS PV module are ^[4]:
- Module efficiency is 9% to 11%.
 - Thickness is 2mm to 4mm substrate material (non-hardened glass) with 3 μ m to 4 μ m coating, of which approximately 1 μ m to 2 μ m CIS.
 - These are dark grey to black in colour.

3.4 4th Generation Solar Cells and Future Trend:

This is the combination of 3rd generation PV cells technologies to form the 4th generation solar cells technology. Example is the Nano crystal /polymer Solar cell, a Composite photo-voltaic Cell technology which combines the elements of the solid state and organic PV cells to form the Hybrid-Nano crystalline oxide polymer composite cell. It is calculated that due to the lower cost of material, this type of solar cell would significantly can make its deployment affordable. Another area of concentrator solar cell technology is proven area where Photo-voltaic solar cell technology has achieved significant efficiency milestone. The Multi-junctions (III-Vs) solar cell has the efficiency of 41% and more. The data of Solar cell efficiency is shown in Figure 6 below shows best research till date (research of NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) and Spectrolab).

4. SOLAR ARRAY MOUNTING AND TRACKING

The conversion efficiency of a solar panel is directly proportional to the total amount of direct solar irradiance that is actually being absorbed. The amount of solar radiation that strikes the surface of a solar cell is known as Irradiance and it is expressed in kW/m². The solar isolation is measured in terms of irradiance multiplied by time. When the solar isolation =1kw/m², it is said to have peak sun hours equal to the number of hours per day. Solar energy absorption is also affected by the effect of atmospheric attenuations, the earth's distance from the sun and the earth tilt angle with respect to the sun. The Azimuth angle is the angle between the true south and the point on the horizon directly below the sun, measured in degrees east or west of true south. The default value of an azimuth angle is 180° for south facing locations in the northern hemisphere. By increasing the azimuth angle, afternoon energy production is maximized. For a single axis tracking system, the azimuth angle is the angle clockwise from true north of the axis of rotation and the azimuth angle for a fixed PV array, is the angle clockwise from true north that the PV array faces. The Azimuth angle for dual axis solar tracking PV arrays is not applicable.

Azimuthal Angles by heading	
Heading Angle	Azimuthal Angle
N	0 or 360
NE	45
E	90
SE	135
S	180
SW	225
W	270
NW	315

Table 1: Azimuthal angle vs heading [1, 3].

The altitude of the sun changes with the time and season throughout the year. The height of the sun above the horizon is termed as altitude of sun. During module or array installations the tilt angle of a solar module with respect to the sun must be carefully considered. Based on the sun’s altitude changes, the general practice for fixed array is that the tilt angle be equal to the latitude, it is recommended that the tilt angle should be adjusted to Latitude + 15° during winter and Latitude-15° during summer for better absorption.

Daily global radiation (MJ m-2 per day) [6]:

CITY	Horizontal Radiation	Optimum tilt Radiation
New Delhi	19.67	21.54
Kolkata	17.47	19.07
Pune	20.4	21.94
Chennai	20.12	20.99

Table 2: Daily global Radiation [6]

5. SOLAR TRACKING

A solar tracker is a device that move or adjust the positional angle of solar photovoltaic panel towards the sun. The sun's position varies both with season and time of day as the sun moves across the sky. Solar panels absorb energy better when orientated perpendicular to the sun, therefore the solar tracker mechanism will essentially increase the effectiveness of solar panels over a fixed solar array or panel.

- Power (W) = VI,
- Irradiance = (W/m²) and
- Insolation = W/m²/day.

Several factors must be considered when determining the use of trackers. Some of these include:

- the solar technology being used,
- the amount of direct solar irradiation available and
- The cost to install and maintain the trackers among others.

Types of tracker:

Trackers can be categorized by the complexity of operation and sophistication. There are two major groups; Active and passive Trackers. Passive trackers are without motor. Active trackers are motorized and can be sub-categorized into single axis and dual axis trackers:

Single axis:

Solar trackers can either have a horizontal or a vertical axis. The horizontal type is used in tropical regions where the sun gets very high at noon, but the days are short. The vertical type is used in high latitudes where the sun does not get very high, but summer days can be very long. In concentrated solar power applications, single axis trackers are used with parabolic and linear Fresnel mirror designs.

Dual axis:

The Dual axis solar trackers have both a horizontal and a vertical axis and thus they can track the sun's apparent motion virtually at any angle. A dual axis tracker maximizes the total power output of solar array by keeping the panels in direct sunlight for the maximum number of hours per day.

Tracker Components:

A typical solar tracking system consist of mechanical parts like the linear actuator with integrated dc or ac motor and gear and an electronic parts like motor drive and controller, sun sensor and power supply. Based on complexity of design and accuracy of tracking, there might be more additional components than those mentioned above.

Fig. 6: A 2-Axis Tracking System [1].

Fixed array Vs Tracked array: A conventional solar array with poly-crystalline solar cells having 14-18% conversion efficiency need area of about 7-8m² to produce a 1KW peak power. Not every applications allow enough space for larger array area and although it is needed to produce sufficient power to meet a desired energy requirement. When a fixed Array, is installed at an angle of the Altitude, many researches showed that the tilt angle adjustment for a fixed array, mounting an array at an optimum angle for a stationary array would generate more power than just using the Altitude angle all year round.

In Figure 6, a 30W solar PV cells array shown mounted at the altitude angle as well as at angle slightly higher than the altitude angle under similar environmental conditions during the beginning of winter 2012. The results show that mounting solar cell at angle higher than the altitude results in up to 5% peak power improvement over the altitude tilt angle.

Promoting light scattering in the visible spectrum: when the light receiving surface of the cell is coated with Nano-sized metallic studs, the efficiency of the cell is considerably increased. As the light reflects off these studs at an oblique angle to the cell, increasing the length of the path the light takes through the cell, thereby increasing the number of photons absorbed by the cell, and so also the amount of current generated.

The materials used for the Nano-studs are silver, gold, and aluminum. Though, gold and silver are not very efficient, because it absorb most of the light in the visible spectrum, which

contains most of the energy present in sunlight. It reduces the amount of light reaching the cell. Aluminum, used in Nano-studs, absorbs only ultraviolet radiation, and reflects both visible and infra-red light, so total loss of energy is minimized. By using Aluminum the efficiency of the cell is increased up to 22% (in lab conditions).

Fig. 7. Temperature in degree Vs Azimuthal angle [1].

2. CONCLUSION

The Nano crystalline technology is estimated to have higher efficiency than the 1st and 2nd generation PV modules. The inverter efficiency plays an important role in module' efficiency including the weather conditions. The array mounting and trackers are the effective technology used for efficiency improvement.

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